

OPEN ACCESS EBOOK USAGE DATA TRUST (OAEBUDT)

Return on Investment (ROI) Case Studies

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About the Open Access Ebook Usage Data Trust (OAEUBDT)

The **OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEUBDT)** is an international effort to facilitate the direct data exchange and benchmarking of open and proprietary usage data about open access (OA) books. The primary goal of the OAEUBDT effort is to address the challenge of aggregating and curating OA book usage data by enabling community-governed sharing of quality, interoperable ebook data.

The project is adopting the **International Data Space (IDS)** model developed by the **International Data Space Association (IDSA)**, which works with the values of:

- increased interoperability
- trust through secure and transparent exchange
- multiparty data governance through usage controls and community-based accountability measures

The “**Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks**” project, sponsored by the Mellon Foundation, aims to formalize the community-governance mechanisms of the Data Trust effort, quantify data trust participation benefits in terms of Return on Investment (ROI), and understand the full operational costs related to international data space for OA book usage.

This project was launched in July 2022, led by Principal Investigators Christina Drummond (University of North Texas), Prodromos Tsiavos (OpenAIRE), and Yannick Legré (OPERAS), and will conclude in late 2025.

About this Study

As part of the “**Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks**” project, the OAEBUDT project team launched a narrow international data space (IDS) pilot in 2025 to test the viability of exchanging COUNTER-compliant usage statistics through the IDS.

The pilot featured six participants:

- JSTOR
- LibLynx
- Knowledge Unlatched
- punctum books
- Ubiquity Press
- Michigan Publishing

Clarke & Esposito (C&E) was engaged to complete a Return on Investment study of pilot participants, to capture the benefits of the IDS integrations and to summarize recommendations to the project team regarding common pain points or areas of opportunity to be used in future integrations.

Study Methodology

- **Project Discovery:** Review of key aspects of Data Trust participation to identify core hypotheses for exploration.
- **Pre-integration interviews** (*occurring at the point the pilot participant began active development of their data trust integration*): A 45- to 60-minute interview with each pilot participant, to capture key goals and expectations of pilot participants.
- **Post-integration interviews** (*following successful integration*): A 45- to 60-minute follow-up interview with each participant to capture feedback (including time and resources needed), as well as gauge time / cost savings opportunities and the degree to which integration met participants’ expectations. Interviewees were invited to answer an optional, brief pre-interview questionnaire (sent in advance of post-integration interviews) to guide discussion.

The results of pre-and post-integration interviews are summarized in this **Case Studies Report**. A final summary of findings and recommendations will follow in the C&E **Return on Investment and Process Improvement Synthesis Report**.

Pilot Integration Overview

The pilot began in February 2025 with the creation of an IDS-compliant data space by OAEBUDT's chosen vendor, Think-It.

Following creation of the data space, pilot participants each integrated with the pilot for the purposes of either *sharing* or *receiving* data with and from other participants.

The role of each pilot participant is outlined in the table shown at right:

- **Data Providers** are those who supplied usage data to another participant through the data space.
- **Data Recipients** are those who received usage data from a provider through the data space.

All integrations focused on sharing of COUNTER-compliant usage data with the appropriate recipient. Each provider executed a participation agreement in advance of their integration to govern the exchange.

Data Provider	Data Recipient
JSTOR	punctum books
JSTOR	Michigan Publishing
Ubiquity Press	Michigan Publishing
Michigan Publishing	LibLynx (<i>on behalf of</i> Knowledge Unlatched)

Pilot Integration Overview (continued)

The diagram below provides a visual representation of the exchange of data between pilot participants, and each organization's role in the OAEBUDT pilot. Each arrow in this figure represents a separate and discrete exchange.

Visualization of OAEBUDT Pilot Integrations

Data Provider

Data supplied to other participant(s)

Data Recipient

Data received from another participant(s)

Dual Role

Participant both supplied and received data during pilot proof of concept

Pilot Case Studies

Case studies of pilot participants reflect findings from C&E pre- and post-integration interviews with key stakeholders from each organization. (A full list of interviewees is included in this report's **Appendix**.)

Each case study is structured to touch on the following elements:

Case Study Element	Description
Organization Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Organization type (university press, independent publisher, digital library, technology provider, etc.)• Organization size (C&E estimate, by revenue: Small = <\$10M, Medium = \$10M-\$100M, Large = \$100M+)• OA book activities• Other activities• Role in OAEUBDT pilot (data recipient, data transfer, or both)
Current State / Project Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Usage reporting collection activities and benefit of usage data to organization• Goals for pilot as described pre-integration
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Feedback on pilot implementation experience, suggested improvements, and limitations• Resources required to complete integration
Pilot Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Assessment of whether integration met project goals, based on post-integration interviews
Return on Investment Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Qualitative overview of anticipated ROI for the OAEBU Data Trust based on experience and findings of pilot integration
Long-Term Outlook	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• OAEBUDT success criteria (e.g., criteria that would promote the organization's further engagement with the data trust following the pilot)• Limitations / blockers (e.g., factors that might prevent further engagement)

Return on Investment (ROI) Qualification

As a highly limited pilot, none of the initial participants completed a “live” integration and therefore this preliminary proof of concept exercise could not be expected to generate a quantitatively calculated ROI.

Therefore, C&E focused this ROI assessment on **anticipated benefit expressed by pilot participants**, based on their experience of the data trust pilot integration. Our qualitative assessment is based on:

- **Investment**, *expected* in determining the ROI of a full data space integration
- **Return**, which can be generated in three ways: *cost savings, revenue growth, or creation of new opportunities* (whether through direct benefit to the organization or indirect benefit that improves the industry as a whole)

A description of how C&E defined each of these elements for our assessment of each case study is shown in this table.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on participant feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Anticipated investment required to complete “live” integration with data space
Return: Cost Savings	Participant expectations of ability to save costs through data space integration
Return: Revenue Growth	Participant expectation of ability to generate new revenue from existing products or services through data space integration
Return: Creation of New Opportunities	Anticipation of whether data space can create new commercial prospects or other strategic benefit (either directly to the organization or indirectly via industry-wide progress)

JSTOR

Participant Profile

JSTOR	
Type of Organization	Non-Profit Digital Library
Organization Size	Large
Open Access Book Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2023, JSTOR launched the Path to Open program offering a new delayed-OA model for participating titles • JSTOR also hosts approximately 14,000 open access books (backlist and current publication)
Other Publication Activities	JSTOR's primary business is hosting journals and books to make them available to institutions; it also offers other hosting services through its JSTOR Digital Stewardship Services
Role in OAEBUDT Pilot	Data Provider (sharing usage data with two participants, Michigan Publishing and punctum books)

JSTOR is part of ITHAKA, a mission-driven non-profit organization serving higher education and academia. JSTOR is one of the largest digital libraries for scholarly content, including journals, books, and other materials. It currently hosts over 2,800 scholarly journals in the humanities, social sciences, and sciences, published by over 1,200 publishers in 57 countries. It also hosts over 158,000 ebooks from over 340 publishers.

JSTOR's current OA books initiative is the Path to Open program, in which approximately 300 participating books per year are hosted DRM-free on a paid-access basis on the JSTOR platform for three

years, after which point they will be converted to fully OA. The Path to Open program launched in 2023, and its first books will be made fully OA next year, in 2026. A number of university presses are participating in the model, including the University of Michigan Press, The University of North Carolina Press, The Ohio State University Press, SUNY Press, Vanderbilt University Press, Liverpool University Press, and Manchester University Press.

JSTOR also offers for-fee hosting of OA books on behalf of publishers (currently at 14,000 OA books available with more being added).

Current State / Project Goals

JSTOR provides usage data to several constituencies, primarily separated into two categories: **publishers** and **libraries**. However, JSTOR notes a broader network beyond these two constituencies with whom JSTOR may or may not have a formal relationship, but who are valuable to consumers of its usage data. Examples include:

- Authors whose books are hosted on JSTOR who might benefit from visibility into how their book is being used
- Open access community programs where JSTOR supports these programs directly, such as Path to Open, or indirectly, such as Knowledge Unlatched and Big Ten Open Books through hosting arrangements for the OA books on their platform. JSTOR anticipates the data trust could establish a mechanism for sharing that data more efficiently and with appropriate safeguards in place

Current usage reporting activities: JSTOR currently manages several tools and products to provide data – for example, an administration site on JSTOR from which users can receive CSV or Excel data; user ability to pull data via the SUSHI protocol; and reports provided via email or FTP. JSTOR notes that this diversity of delivery methods is due to a range of expectations across its many publishers. (JSTOR notes that one delivery method that it has not yet created is delivery of usage data via an API.)

Pilot Participation Goals (Pre-Integration)

- **Support JSTOR’s current constituents**

JSTOR believes that greater visibility into the usage of OA books on its platform will allow it to better illustrate the benefits of initiatives like Path to Open. *“We want to contribute to that community and encourage publishers and authors to make more of their content open.”*

- **Broaden visibility and transparency of usage data**

Through the data trust, JSTOR sees a way to share authoritative usage data with a broader set of constituents, in a way that is transparent and auditable.

- **Standardize definitions of usage data**

Currently, JSTOR must accommodate a variety of reporting formats across providers. JSTOR sees a major benefit of the OAEBUDT initiative as prompting participants to reach a shared understanding of usage data standards (e.g., what can be shared and how it should be shared).

Pilot Implementation

JSTOR reported that the majority of its implementation time was spent on laying out the project for its staff engineers and meeting with Think-It and other providers to coordinate the data exchange. While the development work necessary to complete the integration was less than one week for one engineer, the additional socialization and clarification of the integration's goals and intent meant that integration took in total about 2 weeks of work across 2 FTEs. This is roughly the amount of time originally anticipated for the integration, although JSTOR de-scoped some functionality to stay within its projected budget and timeline.

Implementation Activity	Roles Involved	Total Hours
Completion of data trust agreement	JSTOR legal and program leads	1 week
Technical planning	Engineer / developer; JSTOR program leads	~2 weeks
Development work	Engineer / developer	<1 week
Planning / Meetings	Engineer / developer; JSTOR program leads	~2 weeks

Total Implementation Time = 2 weeks, 2 FTE

Process feedback: JSTOR initially struggled with documentation but had success following the provision of how-to videos laying out the necessary steps.

Improvements suggested: JSTOR felt integration would have been easier for its development team if provided a clearer articulation of the problems and use cases of the data space.

Limitations:

- JSTOR took a “minimum viable product” approach and so their initial integration was partial: it did not represent a full “live” buildout of their capabilities. Further development work would be required to create this full integration.
- JSTOR notes that identity and access management – i.e., agreement across providers about the organizational identifier system used to identify data recipients and institutions – remains a significant open question.

Pilot Outcomes

As a result of integrating with the pilot, JSTOR was able to send usage data to two of its current publishers (punctum books and Michigan Publishing). JSTOR took a “minimum viable product” approach to its pilot integration, establishing its ability to provide a single, static report through the data trust to each of its participating publishers. JSTOR noted that additional development work would be required for a more robust integration. From a technical standpoint, this constituted success of the proof of concept: the data trust is a viable mechanism for data exchange.

The primary missing piece noted by JSTOR is a demonstration of how the data trust would improve on current workflows for its existing publishers. Until *all* of its constituents participate in the data trust, JSTOR would need to support both its current methods of report retrieval *and* the data trust. Rather than creating efficiencies, this would result in some duplication of effort for JSTOR’s technical teams which would need to be justified by a strong business case (e.g., a critical mass of participation).

Goal	Description of Progress
Support JSTOR’s current publishers	JSTOR confirmed the technical feasibility of data sharing through the data trust, but anticipated challenges with establishing the trust as the primary (and only) method of data exchange.
Broaden visibility and transparency of usage data	In the pilot, JSTOR exchanged data with two of its existing publishers; while there is potential for significant benefits from exchanging data with additional parties without direct JSTOR relationships, these were not proven out in the proof of concept.
Standardization of usage data	The data space itself will not require usage data standardization – providers are expected to send data through the trust “as-is”, along with trust indicators illustrating the quality of the data.

Return on Investment Assessment

Like many other pilot participants, JSTOR views the ROI of data trust integration as contingent on a critical mass of participating providers. However, JSTOR expressed more specific concerns about the needs of its smaller publishers, whom JSTOR must support regardless of their ability to integrate with the data trust. Without full participation from its publishers, JSTOR would need to support multiple methods for report generation which reduces the potential for efficiency gains.

JSTOR also noted that the data trust project will not address standardization of key elements, like usage reporting elements or identity management of institutions and users. (The data trust itself does not dictate a specific reporting standard, so a separate initiative would be required to achieve this goal.) JSTOR anticipates the time/effort of standardization would be high, further jeopardizing the potential for a positive ROI.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Actual amount unknown based on pilot, but may be significant
Return: Cost Savings	No immediate cost savings; JSTOR would need to support both the data trust and its current methods of data provision until all publishers integrated into the data trust
Return: Revenue Growth	None noted
Return: Creation of New Opportunities	JSTOR anticipated that the data trust could incentivize greater data standardization, but that the cost of this standardization could be high

JSTOR views itself as having an important responsibility to support its diverse constituents and anticipates further participation in the data trust would require clarity and agreement among its constituents about shared benefits and standards used.

	Long Term Value Proposition <i>Results anticipated following proof of concept</i>
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Demand from JSTOR’s publishers. For JSTOR to realize any efficiency gains from the data trust, JSTOR publishers must also participate. To do this, publishers need a clear understanding of the problems to be uniquely solved by the data trust and the capability to invest in their own integration.• Standardization of data reporting and attributes. JSTOR noted that many of its constituents require data in disparate and customized formats, across multiple providers. The data trust initiative does not anticipate requiring harmonization of reporting across providers, which JSTOR considered an important prerequisite to unlock the value of usage data sharing.
Limitations / Blockers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Significant additional technical work would be necessary. JSTOR’s “minimum viable product” integration did not reflect a full realization of the data trust’s potential.• Agreement upon organizational identifier standards. It is unclear what system will be in place to commonly identify institutional users at a highly granular level. While this capability is extremely valuable, JSTOR anticipates adoption of any new organizational identifier standard across providers would increase development cost of a more robust OAEBUDT integration.

LibLynx

Participant Profile

LibLynx	
Type of Organization	Service Provider (identity, access, and analytics management)
Organization Size	Small
Open Access Book Activities	LibLynx currently receives and processes data from 7 book aggregators as a part of a pilot project with university presses
Other Publication Activities	LibLynx's services are largely format-agnostic, so its clients also include journal publishers and others in the scholarly publishing ecosystem
Role in OAEBUDT Pilot	Data Recipient <i>in an intermediary role</i> (receiving usage data from Michigan Publishing on behalf of Knowledge Unlatched)

LibLynx serves a variety of clients with usage analytics, processing over one billion events per year. Its publisher clients range from those managing their own platform, those reliant on third-party platform providers to host a proprietary platform, and those without a dedicated ebooks platform who are reliant on third-party aggregators and distributors. LibLynx's role is to receive raw event data, process it into useful metrics, and then use those metrics to provide reports in COUNTER or another custom format to their publisher clients or to their stakeholders.

LibLynx's services mean it plays an interesting and unique role within the OAEBUDT pilot: it fulfills neither the trust's definition of a data producer (it does not produce its own data, it processes data from other sources) nor that of a data recipient (it processes data for the purpose of providing to the ultimate recipient). However, because many OA book publishers outsource usage analysis and reporting to LibLynx and do not currently have their own capabilities, LibLynx plays a meaningful role in the OA books supply chain.

Current State / Project Goals

LibLynx's support for the OAEBUDT pilot is motivated by an overall interest in improving the value of usage data throughout the scholarly publishing industry. LibLynx is involved in several other OA books projects and pilots, including a pilot with 7 university presses to aggregate usage across multiple platforms (JSTOR, MUSE, Paradigm, etc.). This makes LibLynx familiar with the complexities of processing and unifying data across multiple parties, and the "thorny" challenges of aggregating usage files that are in different formats across different providers. The hope is that initiatives like OAEBUDT can help to reduce the cost and complexity of usage data sharing, especially for smaller organizations with fewer resources which might otherwise struggle to make sense of the data.

That said, LibLynx also identified a key challenge that OAEBUDT might face, which is the lack of consistency and quality of usage data across platforms. LibLynx has observed that certain platforms' system limitations mean that those platforms are not equipped to provide consistent or meaningful data to outside parties. Without these capabilities to provide consistent and quality usage data, the data trust will have less valuable information to exchange. LibLynx therefore aims to support any initiative – including OAEBUDT – which can incentivize platforms to create better infrastructure and standardization around usage data capture and reporting.

Pilot Participation Goals (Pre-Integration)

- **Incentivize improvements to ebook usage data reporting**
LibLynx notes that many publishers are provided limited or incomplete data about usage of their titles on third-party platforms, due to reporting limitations of those platforms. Its hope is that the data trust will incentivize providers to improve both the *quantity* and *quality* of data made available.
- **Unlock potential of improved usage analytics**
LibLynx's long-term goal is to enable OA book publishers to develop more meaningful analytics based on usage and other activities, beyond that currently available today. *"There is a lot of hidden value in open access books that is not accessible because of the difficulties in demonstrating the value of opening these books."*
- **Support for publicly accessible usage sharing infrastructure**
LibLynx also views community infrastructure as "a public good" worth pursuing beyond its own commercial interests, for the betterment of the scholarly publishing industry as a whole.

Pilot Implementation

LibLynx’s integration with the pilot / proof-of-concept did not require development work and was completed by a non-technical Client Success employee. This was largely due to the data trust’s provision of a lightweight API connector (PostMan); a more robust integration would likely require additional development work to be complete.

Implementation Activity	Roles Involved	Total Hours
Completion of data trust agreement	Client Success, CEO	1.5
Technical planning	Client Success, CTO	2
Development work	None	Not applicable
Documentation	Client Success	3
Data Connector setup and test	Client Success	5
Data Trust committee meetings	Client success	5

Total Implementation Time = 16.5 hours

Process feedback: LibLynx reported that the steps outlined in the documentation provided were clear and easy to follow, even for non-technical participants. The pilot integration required some direct coordination (e.g., virtual meetings with counterparts at Michigan Publishing), which presumably would not be necessary for a “live” product.

Improvements suggested: LibLynx anticipated additional project management support would be helpful to coordinate steps and timelines, especially with multiple parties involved. In addition, LibLynx’s participation in the pilot as an intermediary between data providers and recipients highlighted a gap in role definitions which could be addressed in future.

Limitations:

- As noted above, LibLynx anticipates a full integration into the data trust would not rely on the Postman API connector but would involve LibLynx building out its own APIs. This would require significantly more work and the involvement of LibLynx’s technical development team.
- LibLynx also anticipated it would need to develop a more automated system of alerts for each of these calls, to provide visibility into system performance and enable troubleshooting where necessary.

Pilot Outcomes

LibLynx’s integration in the data trust allowed it to receive data from Michigan Publishing on behalf of mutual partner Knowledge Unlatched. Though LibLynx also provides reporting services for clients, it did not act as a data provider intermediary for the purposes of this pilot.

Because LibLynx and Michigan Publishing are already partners, the pilot did not establish any new exchange of data between them. Given the limited scope for the integration, LibLynx anticipates no changes to its current workflows with Michigan Publishing. However,

the pilot was important in demonstrating new paths for potential data exchange with LibLynx, particularly for providers with limited technical capabilities or who do not currently have a direct relationship with LibLynx –moving from reliance on bilateral data exchange between two parties to a more federated structure. For providers integrated into the data trust, a technical connection between parties becomes easier particularly between stakeholders who do not already have a direct partnership or contractual relationship.

Goal	Description of Progress
Incentivize improvements to ebook usage data reporting	LibLynx describes the primary benefit of the pilot as “the socialization of better and more accurate data sharing.” While the pilot did not specifically address reporting structure, support for the data trust is a first step in encouraging providers and platforms to address limitations in data reporting.
Unlock potential of improved usage analytics	Data shared through the trust was not standardized and the format was determined by the data provider. LibLynx sees more potential for improvement with the data trust and with better standardization and expansion of usage data reporting capabilities.
Support for publicly accessible usage sharing infrastructure	LibLynx saw the pilot as successful from a “social good” perspective. <i>“Our goal is to support showing that the data trust could share data, so if the pilot is successful from a data exchange perspective that’s a good thing.”</i>

Return on Investment Assessment

By nature of its core services, LibLynx already has strong technical connections with its clients and partners and is already receiving and distributing a large amount of usage data today. The data trust does not create any greater efficiencies in these processes for LibLynx itself. Instead, the data trust represents for LibLynx an increase in potential to connect with organizations where there is not currently a formal partnership, and to provide an incentive to

enhance reporting systems to make full use of the data available. The benefit to LibLynx is therefore conditional on increased adoption throughout the industry and further investment in standardization and enhancement of usage data by all participating parties. In this case, the most important measure is the ROI to organizations, particularly data providers, who would need to invest more significant resources in order to participate.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Further investment would be necessary in better automation and a more robust API structure
Return: Cost Savings	LibLynx does not see the data trust as a source for greater efficiency
Return: Revenue Growth	None noted for existing partnerships
Return: Creation of New Opportunities	Primary benefit of the data trust is ability to build connections and share a more robust level of data with organizations where there is no formal relationship in place today

LibLynx highly recommends future participation in the data trust to others. In fact, future participation from a wide variety of participants is critical to the data trust’s success. This is true not only among publishers of OA books, but also (potentially) for a wider audience if the data trust expanded to other forms of usage data (for example for paid-access books, journals, and so on).

	Long Term Value Proposition <i>Results anticipated following proof of concept</i>
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization of usage data provision. Though out of scope for the pilot, LibLynx anticipates that the current inconsistency in usage data capture between platforms and providers could hold back the data trust’s full potential. (The data space will not require a minimum standard of data, but participants will be encouraged to share more and better usage data to fully capture the benefits.) Expansion of data space roles. It is important for the data trust to fully reflect the many roles within the OA books supply chain it is designed to serve. According to the data trust’s definition, LibLynx is neither a data producer nor data recipient (it serves both functions only on behalf of its clients). In future, LibLynx recommends broadening definitions or creating a new term that embraces third-party data handlers like LibLynx.
Limitations / Blockers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data trust must remain accessible to a broad range of organizations. LibLynx acknowledges that to fully participate commercially in the data trust, it would need to extend its own systems. It is important that a full data trust integration remain accessible to organizations who do not have LibLynx’s technical capabilities or wherewithal, and that the benefits are made clear to any organization who might choose to invest work or time into the trust. Openness to greater data sharing. LibLynx notes that many of the blockers for data trust participation relate to potential participants’ own willingness to make their usage data available beyond established bilateral agreements.

punctum books

Participant Profile

punctum books	
Type of Organization	Independent Non-Profit Publisher
Organization Size	Small
Open Access Book Activities	~30 titles per year, all OA (excluding corresponding print versions)
Other Publication Activities	None; punctum is 100% focused on books and publishes entirely on a Diamond OA basis
Role in OAEBUDT Pilot	Data Recipient (receiving usage data from its distribution partner, JSTOR)

punctum books was founded in 2011 as a fully open access and scholar-led press focusing on humanities, social sciences, fine arts, and architecture / design. It publishes roughly 30 titles per year under a Diamond OA model, in which books are made free to read with no fees to either the author or to libraries. It is primarily sustained by library memberships with additional income from print book sales of OA titles, and incremental revenue from reader donations / memberships, grants, etc.

punctum books stands out among OAEBUDT pilot participants for several reasons: first, it is the smallest organization to participate, with less than \$500K in revenues per year. At this size, punctum runs

a correspondingly lean operation with limited capacity for significant technical development work. Second, it is the only organization with a complete focus on open access books. Lastly, punctum books has been among the most active participants and supporters of other infrastructure development within the OA books space, particularly to support small- to medium-sized publishers. punctum's co-director is currently serving as Director/CEO of Thoth Open Metadata and is working with partners at OAPEN, COKI, OPERAS, U of M Press, and DOAB to develop an open source usage dashboard (which may be an eventual consumer of usage data such as that shared via OAEBUDT).

Current State / Project Goals

punctum describes usage of its OA titles as important to its ability to communicate with authors, as well as to underpin its library support model in which libraries use part of their collections budgets to sponsor continued Diamond OA publication. To support access to this data, punctum makes its usage statistics publicly available via visualization dashboards available on its website (<https://punctumbooks.com/usage-statistics/>). In addition to the dashboards, which are built on open source software, punctum has published several blog posts detailing the system and important caveats. (One of the most important caveats: the disparity of data representation across providers, making the data sources difficult if not impossible to reconcile.)

Current usage reporting activities: punctum currently gathers usage data from other platforms where its titles are made available (OAPEN, JSTOR, Project MUSE, Google Books). Each month, the press co-director is responsible for gathering usage data, processing into its preferred format, and uploading to a MYSQL database.

Given the manual nature of data collection, one of the biggest challenges encountered by punctum is when providers make unannounced changes to the format of usage reporting. Such changes typically require reformatting of the data or reprogramming of the usage dashboards to accommodate the new format. Each time an altered report requires troubleshooting or reformatting, it requires roughly 2.5 hours of work by punctum's co-director.

Pilot Participation Goals (Pre-Integration)

- **Establish a proof of concept of data transfer protocols**
punctum considers a neutral industry-led protocol for the transfer of these data “absolutely necessary” to replace current inefficient methods of data delivery (emails, CSV files, etc.).
- **Support open infrastructure for OA books**
Support for OAEBUDT is consistent with punctum's support of other community-led initiatives, and punctum's leadership in sharing its knowledge with others in the industry. The protocol enabling OAEBUDT is viewed by punctum as highly complementary to efforts to build open source and community-led ebook usage analytics services, such as that explored by the Open Book Collective and Thoth Open Metadata. (It is likely that punctum would move its own usage reporting infrastructure to the new open source dashboard when it is complete.)

Pilot Implementation

punctum did not require any technical work to integrate with the data space pilot as a data recipient. Following JSTOR’s integration, punctum was able to confirm that the usage report transmitted from JSTOR was received through the data space. The majority of the time and effort required of punctum was participation in a Zoom meeting to establish the technical connection with JSTOR and to receive the resulting report through the API.

Implementation Activity	Roles Involved	Total Hours
Completion of data trust agreement	Co-Director	Not captured
Technical planning	Not required	Not applicable
Development work	Not required	Not applicable
Planning / Meetings	Co-Director	<minimal>

Total Implementation Time = <minimal>

Process feedback: punctum reported that documentation supporting their integration was “extensive and comprehensive”, and “organized in a sensible way.”

Improvements suggested: Creation of a user interface might be helpful, although only required to serve non-technical users (will not be necessary for use by developers).

Limitations:

- punctum did not coordinate with JSTOR in advance about report format, so the sample report did not contain some of the standard metadata elements typically shared with punctum. As the data exchange was intended as a proof of concept, this did not pose an issue.
- In a “live” integration, punctum anticipates that there would be negotiation with JSTOR on the amount and level of data to be shared, and the data would be provided in a machine interpretable format to fully eliminate the need for manual work.

Pilot Outcomes

punctum described the IDS pilot as having a positive outcome in terms of establishing a proof of concept for a neutral, community-supported protocol for data exchange. This was punctum’s primary goal of the integration and consistent with punctum’s mission. In the words of our interviewee: *“punctum books is always ready to work on these types of grassroots initiatives to establish open infrastructures.”* This represents a long-term benefit in punctum’s view: this protocol is capable of persisting and being adopted in many contexts, with or without the continuation of the OAEBUDT initiative.

The strongest benefits envisioned by punctum were not directly to its own organization, but rather to the broader OA books industry as a whole. In post-integration interviews, punctum reiterated the benefit to parallel initiatives like open source usage dashboards, and the opportunity the data space poses to improve data sharing to such tools. punctum’s expectation is that it would not be an adopter of the data space directly, but would be an adopter of the tools that might gather data through the data space.

Goal	Description of Progress
Establish a proof of concept of data transfer protocols	Successful data transfer between JSTOR and punctum books is proof that the data exchange protocol works as designed.
Support open infrastructure for OA books	punctum books’ participation in the pilot enabled the protocol to be developed and provided important expertise in the early stages of developing this open infrastructure.

Return on Investment Assessment

Case Study: punctum books

Despite its role in the pilot phase, punctum books does not anticipate it would directly integrate into a “live” data space. Rather, punctum anticipates using and supporting related usage analytics services. Despite the success of the pilot, this suggests a low expected level of investment of the data space for punctum, and also makes any anticipated returns highly conditional on further integration with the data space by other participants.

In other words, a positive ROI for punctum would only be possible if the data trust successfully increases scale and receives support from larger organizations to provide a critical mass of usage data exchange.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Low – does not expect to integrate directly
Return: Cost Savings	Savings would be achieved if protocol were adopted by open source book analytics tools and the providers serving data to those tools
Return: Revenue Growth	None anticipated
Return: Create New Opportunities	punctum books expects benefits will most likely accrue generally throughout the industry through the proof of concept of this open infrastructure

punctum’s most important success criterion for the data trust – one that would merit further investment – is broader adoption among a range of stakeholders; small publishers like punctum are unlikely to be fiscally or operationally equipped to be the sole support for this initiative. punctum acknowledges that broader adoption may even include exchange of data more broadly (“this could be a solution for your entire flow of usage data”), which they believe would be fully supported by the protocol based on the pilot proof of concept.

	Long Term Value Proposition <i>Results anticipated following proof of concept</i>
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Broader adoption of the data space protocol. punctum recognizes that efficiency gains from use of the protocol relies on greater scale, in which providers sharing large amounts of data with each other mutually adopt the protocol.• Expansion to other forms of data exchange. Given the need for broader adoption as a success criteria of the data trust, punctum anticipates that expansion may need to involve support for larger data flows than those supporting open access monographs.
Limitations / Blockers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• As a small press, punctum books is unlikely to complete a full integration directly. punctum anticipates that it would benefit from the data space through use of resources like the Thoth Open Metadata book analytics dashboard, rather than a direct integration.• Sustainability. Additional participants are necessary to ensure adequate funding for the data space and protocol, which requires a clear value proposition for all participants. Small- to medium-sized publishers like punctum are not likely sufficient to provide financial sustainability, given their limited resources.

Ubiquity Press

Participant Profile

Case Study: Ubiquity Press

Ubiquity Press	
Type of Organization	OA publisher and publishing service provider; part of the Paradigm Publishing Services division of De Gruyter Brill (commercial publisher / service provider)
Organization Size	Large
Open Access Book Activities	De Gruyter / Ubiquity host the University Press Library Open (UPLO) platform, launched in April 2024, as one of the largest online collections of free-to-read academic books; UPLO is supported via a collective action model overseen by a separate not-for-profit established by De Gruyter, ebound
Other Publication Activities	De Gruyter is a publisher of books and journals, and Paradigm Publishing Services offers distribution / sales support and other publishing services for journals and monographs under a variety of business models
Role in OAEBUDT Pilot	Data Provider (sending usage data to Michigan Publishing)

Ubiquity was acquired by De Gruyter in 2022 and became part of De Gruyter's Paradigm Publishing Services division at its establishment in 2023. Ubiquity is both a publisher and a service provider: Ubiquity Press is a fully open access publisher supporting different models of OA (gold, diamond). Ubiquity is a provider of infrastructure and services to university presses and institutional repositories.

In addition to its support of open access and open science, Ubiquity is a strong supporter and developer of open source technologies and community infrastructure. Among its other activities, Ubiquity is the service provider for OPERAS Metrics, a database of usage and impact metrics for OA books funded by the OPERAS consortium and currently used by ~10 European publishers.

Current State / Project Goals

Ubiquity has significant experience working with usage data from disparate sources, given its years of support for OPERAS Metrics. Through this initiative, Ubiquity has successfully worked to retrieve and combine usage data to illustrate the impact of open content (usage being “the new currency” for OA books). Some of the challenges noted from this experience include:

- Inconsistent access to data – for example, cases of formerly open data sources like Twitter shutting down their APIs
- Inability to access important data directly, because the publisher hosts that title on a platform with no direct relationship or data exchange with Ubiquity
- Inconsistent standards around usage reporting and difficulty comparing metrics across platforms

Separate from its role as a data collector for OPERAS Metrics, De Gruyter / Ubiquity hosts the University Press Library Open platform (UPLO), which must routinely report usage to participating partner presses.

Current usage reporting activities: Currently reporting for each press is handled manually and requires 1-2 days of work per quarter. This role as a data provider is another opportunity for generating a return from the data trust, if the time/effort costs of this process can be reduced through participation.

Pilot Participation Goals (Pre-Integration)

- **Maintain access to a broader set of usage data sources**
Ubiquity’s experience with the OPERAS database has taught it the importance of reliable access to a diversity of data sources, particularly those third parties hosting titles on a partner’s behalf. It is hoped that the data trust will create structure and formalization around data sharing to increase access to data from these sources.
- **Improve reporting capabilities for partner presses**
As a service provider working on behalf of publisher partners, Ubiquity Press aims to integrate with the data space to improve what information is made available for titles hosted on its platforms.
- **Reduced labor cost of partner usage reporting**
Currently, reporting to UPLO partners still requires some manual intervention. A valuable outcome of the data trust would be a reduction of these steps to enable more automated delivery of usage data to UPLO’s 30+ partner presses and to presses in Ubiquity's Partner Network.

Pilot Implementation

Ubiquity approached the pilot integration with an understanding that it was primarily an initial proof-of-concept, with room for further development and iteration in future. The integration took a total of 12.5 hours, which they found to be a reasonable amount for the work completed.

Their expectation is that a more robust integration would require additional development work, but they also anticipated that the 12.5 hours already spent would not need to be duplicated in future iterations.

Implementation Activity	Roles Involved	Total Hours
Completion of data trust agreement	<i>Not captured</i>	<i>Not captured</i>
Technical planning	<i>Not captured</i>	<i>Not captured</i>
Development work	<i>Not captured</i>	<i>Not captured</i>
Planning / Meetings	<i>Not captured</i>	<i>Not captured</i>

Total Implementation Time = 12.5 hours

Process feedback: Ubiquity Press reported that their implementation was straightforward, and they were able to walk step by step through the process easily using the provided documentation. They found the API to be well-constructed and all necessary information was there to complete the transaction.

Improvements suggested: Ubiquity recommends in future that there be more visibility in confirming that all steps had been completed correctly. Furthermore, Ubiquity recommends a more bespoke API client be used for the exchange in lieu of Postman, to ensure the project remains scalable.

Limitations:

- As noted above, Ubiquity anticipates that although the implementation was sufficient for a proof-of-concept for the data exchange, additional development work would be required to take advantage of full data space functionality.

Pilot Outcomes

As a result of the pilot, Ubiquity (serving as a data provider) was able to send usage data from UPLO to the Michigan Publishing (the data recipient) for their 12 titles hosted on UPLO.

Ubiquity considered the pilot to be a success from a proof-of-concept point of view. Though the exchange with Michigan Publishing required some direct coordination, these steps would, in theory, be automated or abstracted with a “live” integration. There were several other improvements (see previous “Pilot Implementation” section) that would also be necessary should the project continue to scale.

For the purposes of establishing a basic exchange, the pilot was sufficient.

Ubiquity did note that future development of the data trust might begin to increase the complexity of the technology. From their perspective, it will be important that the trust remain accessible to organizations with limited technical expertise. This may require dedicated IT resources and oversight dedicated to OAEBUDT (whether via OAEBUDT staff or external support), which raises questions of financial sustainability and long-term costs to participants.

Goal	Description of Progress
Maintain access to a broader set of usage data sources	Ubiquity saw that the proof of concept streamlined the permissions structure around access to data in a way that made sense and held promise for the data trust if scaled.
Improve reporting capabilities for partner presses	Ubiquity reported that the data trust architecture is more complex than parallel initiatives such as OPERAS Metrics. The potential for additional granularity of data is what sets the data trust pilot apart; that said, Ubiquity noted that the data trust must remain accessible and sustainable for a variety of organizations, despite this complexity.
Reduced labor cost of partner usage reporting	While the pilot did not result in capabilities that would immediately reduce the time and effort for usage reporting, Ubiquity hopes that this might be addressed in future iterations.

Return on Investment Assessment

Ubiquity notes that the greater promise of the data trust also relies on sufficient resourcing: *“Such an organization must be funded, managed, especially if the evolution of this project is projected over three, five, ten years. There needs to be a plan to make sure this is funded in the longer run, otherwise we may be building something that is not sustainable.”*

Ubiquity also encouraged coordination with parallel initiatives, to ensure that there was not duplication of effort and to take advantage of synergies and opportunities to further streamline investment and research into shared problems.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Ubiquity anticipates additional work would be required for a full integration, both for data trust participants and on the data trust itself
Return: Cost Savings	Further automation remains a goal for Ubiquity though not realized due to the limited scope of the proof of concept
Return: Revenue Growth	None noted
Return: Creation of New Opportunities	Ubiquity viewed the data trust as more robust than parallel initiatives which would increase the amount of data available; this corresponds with increased complexity and a need for additional resourcing to remain sustainable

Long Term Outlook

Ubiquity sees a continued need for greater usage data sharing throughout the scholarly publishing industry, and a growing demand for access to these data among institutions and universities. The ability to expand access to data for these stakeholders is only going to become more important over time. However, to succeed the data trust must provide an accessible and sustainable path forward for potential participants, and receive real community buy in, before organizations will be able to realize a return on their investment in the project.

	Long Term Value Proposition <i>Results anticipated following proof of concept</i>
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower barriers to entry. To move beyond the proof of concept, Ubiquity believes it is important for the data trust to be as accessible as possible, lowering barriers to entry for organizations without deep technical expertise. • Wide participation. To be successful, the data trust requires community buy in, especially from larger organizations that can provide not only a critical mass of data but also a critical mass of financial support and resourcing. If wide participation is not achieved it is more likely that infrastructure will be developed in a more splintered fashion, making it harder to achieve the network effects of a community-driven resource.
Limitations / Blockers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear and sustainable resourcing. For organizations to invest in the data trust requires some degree of confidence in the long-term sustainability of the initiative, to ensure that those investments will continue to accrue over the long term.

Michigan Publishing

Participant Profile

Michigan Publishing	
Type of Organization	University Press (University of Michigan Press [UMP]); Platform provider (Fulcrum)
Organization Size	Medium
Open Access Book Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Michigan Publishing supports Fulcrum, a monograph-based publishing platform that supports both open and restricted content; several Fulcrum clients are fully-OA publishers (Amherst College Press, Lever Press)• University of Michigan Press hosts its own ebook collections on Fulcrum, including OA books supported through its Fund to Mission program (a collective action model)
Other Publication Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• In addition to hosting OA books, Fulcrum also hosts restricted content like the ACLS Humanities and British Archeological Reports collections• While Fund to Mission supports publication of 75% of UMP's books output as OA, the remaining 25% remain available under a paid-access model
Role in OAEBUDT Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data Recipient (receiving usage data from its distribution partner, JSTOR)• Data Provider (sending usage data to funder / distribution partner, Knowledge Unlatched, via LibLynx)

Michigan Publishing is part of the University of Michigan Libraries and is comprised of three entities: University of Michigan Press (UMP; a publisher of books and educational materials); Michigan Publishing Services (which offers professional publishing services for University of Michigan staff, faculty, and students); and the Deep Blue Repositories and Research Data Services.

UMP's primary OA books initiative is the Fund to Mission model, a collective action model in which the press commits to publishing 75% of its annual scholarly books output as fully OA assuming annual funding targets are met. Michigan Publishing also supports Fulcrum, a community-based, open-source publishing platform used by the UMP as well as 18 publisher partners ranging from university presses, museums, and open educational resource (OER) initiatives.

Current State / Project Goals

Michigan Publishing sees the availability of usage data as central to its ability to scale OA book activity. There are several sources of demand for this data:

- Authors wishing to understand the performance of their titles
- Fulcrum publisher clients, interested in the performance of their titles on the platform
- Library customers assessing their own institution's usage to make purchase decisions
- Funders assessing the ROI of publication support for OA titles

Current usage reporting activities: To increase the efficiency of its data sharing, Michigan Publishing works with ScholarlyIQ (SiQ), a provider of COUNTER-compliant reports. Michigan Publishing partnered with SiQ once it realized there was more efficiency in outsourcing data sharing to a third party than in building and maintaining a COUNTER-compliant dashboard of their own. Currently, Michigan Publishing has nine dashboards set up for publishers on SiQ.

Michigan Publishing also makes its usage available via IRUS and other dashboards such as the Books Analytics Service operated by OAPEN. It anticipates continuing to make its data available through these sources as well as any new sources that are launched. Michigan Publishing's goal for participating in the OAEBUDT Data Trust is to ensure it can efficiently scale its ability to respond to an increasing number of requests for data – while managing requests is possible today, Michigan Publishing envisions a time when current processes are no longer sufficient.

Pilot Participation Goals (Pre-Integration)

- **Efficient sharing of usage information**
Data sharing is important to Michigan Publishing to “tell the story of open access and its impact.”
- **Ensure scalability of data sharing**
Michigan Publishing is currently an active sharer of its OA books usage data, but anticipates it will soon reach a limit on its ability to scale: *“There is a point at which manual management of these data sources becomes impossible to do.”*
- **Support better books analytics services**
Michigan Publishing has made many efforts to ensure its data are available and visible to stakeholders including authors, libraries, and publishers, both through report provision and in support for publicly visible dashboards, such as the Books Analytics Service operated by OAPEN.

Pilot Implementation

Michigan Publishing initially explored a pilot implementation via its current third-party service provider, Scholarly IQ (SiQ). However, it was determined that SiQ participation would be out of scope for the pilot given the complexity of navigating the data trust agreements required. Michigan Publishing opted instead to integrate directly with the data space.

Michigan Publishing did not require any technical work to integrate with the data space pilot as a data recipient or a data provider. Time estimates shown below include exploratory conversations with SiQ, leading up to the decision to participate without SiQ involvement.

Implementation Activity	Roles Involved	Total Hours
Completion of data trust agreement	Procurement, Publisher	3
Technical planning	SiQ Rep and Technical Teams; Michigan Publishing Project Lead; Platform Technology Lead	7 (5 hours negotiating with SiQ, 2 hours documentation)
Development work	<i>Not required</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Planning / Meetings	SiQ Rep and Technical Teams; Michigan Publishing Project Lead	5

Total Implementation Time = 15 hours

As a result of integrating with the pilot, Michigan Publishing was able to receive usage data from its digital library partner (JSTOR) and transfer usage data to book distributor / funder (Knowledge Unlatched, via LibLynx).

Process feedback: Michigan Publishing reported the integration itself was “easy, even for a non-technical person.”

Improvements suggested: Michigan Publishing recommended that other providers bear in mind the complexities of working through the data sharing agreement, especially given the novelty of the data space concept within the industry.

Limitations:

- Because Michigan Publishing did not complete the pilot via its third party vendor SiQ, there were no external costs associated with the implementation. It is possible a later integration may require additional costs.

Pilot Outcomes

Michigan Publishing reported pilot participation as extremely helpful in learning more about the data trust and gaining a more concrete understanding of the benefits of participation. For example, Michigan Publishing identified new capabilities offered by the data trust it does not have in place today: specifically, an auditable record of usage data transactions, which allows Michigan Publishing to better track what data it has sent to whom. Michigan Publishing's perspective on the data trust changed following the integration: *"The number one [benefit] is retaining ownership to this increasingly precious resource. Number two is [knowing] where your data is."*

This reflects a shift in Michigan Publishing's expectations around potential benefits; now, reporting efficiency is seen as less of a benefit of the data trust (at least in this iteration), as the potential for reporting efficiency requires a critical mass of data trust adoption to be realized. Furthermore, Michigan Publishing has already sought efficiency in data sharing through its third-party integration with SiQ, and the data trust did not appear to create any further improvements to this relationship (in fact, SiQ was not part of the initial integration due cost and to the complexity of striking the appropriate agreements).

Goal	Description of Progress
Reporting Efficiency	Because Michigan Publishing currently works with SiQ, little efficiency was gained in the pilot. Further efficiencies would be conditional on increasing scale of data trust participation.
Ability to Scale	As with reporting efficiency, scalability requires a critical mass of participation to be realized. However, Michigan Publishing did note the added benefit of data exchange auditability and visibility as benefits of participation not originally anticipated, that would be especially compelling as the volume of data exchange increases.
Support Books Analytics Services	As noted, Michigan Publishing's ability to realize this benefit presumes that those books analytics services themselves participate in the data trust and can receive all necessary usage data via this method.

Return on Investment Assessment

Michigan Publishing had a different perspective on data trust investment following its integration: whereas initially Michigan Publishing expected the data trust to be “deep infrastructure”, now it is the increased trackability of data sharing that is seen as the benefit which might increase the short-term ROI. The data trust is “much higher in the infrastructure stack” (i.e., has more immediate and practical utility) than originally expected.

Of course, realizing the full benefit of the data trust requires other providers to participate alongside Michigan Publishing, so whether there is short- or long-term benefit depends heavily on the timing of data trust expansion. Michigan Publishing sees the pilot as successful in creating tangible visibility into potential use cases for the trust, which is essential to encouraging that broader adoption.

	Anticipated Return on Investment <i>Based on feedback following proof of concept</i>
Level of Investment	Additional costs are expected for full implementation; the actual amount is unknown
Return: Cost Savings	Meaningful savings are anticipated even if only a portion of custom requests can be directed through the data trust; this ROI is conditional on higher industry uptake
Return: Revenue Growth	None noted
Return: Creation of New Opportunities	Michigan Publishing saw significant value in ability to better track / audit data sharing, which are capabilities not available today

Long-Term Outlook

Michigan Publishing acknowledged the difficulty of funding infrastructure investments like that of the data trust, especially in the present moment (funding cuts at universities, consolidation or re-organization among vendors, discontinuation of related key initiatives). Overall, Michigan Publishing was optimistic that the data trust could be successful and impactful across many types of data providers – *provided it can gain enough adoption*.

	Long Term Value Proposition <i>Results anticipated following proof of concept</i>
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Critical mass of adoption. Michigan Publishing sees the benefits of the data trust as requiring a critical mass of participation – this could be adoption by a number of smaller providers, or adoption by one large provider (Amazon’s adoption of the ONIX standard for book distribution and the corresponding increase of importance for ONIX delivery was cited as an example).• Expansion to other data types. Michigan Publishing expects the benefits of the data trust to extend beyond OA books, to any data output where increased visibility and trackability of data exchange is necessary. An example shared is keeping track of which books have been shared for AI training, with which partners, for what period, and for which purposes.
Limitations / Blockers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• “Chicken or the egg” problem of adoption. Michigan Publishing acknowledged in our interview that the ROI for adoption requires a critical mass of participation, but participation requires an ROI that can only be achieved through broad adoption.• Communication of benefits of the data trust. Further investment in the data trust must come with an articulation of direct benefits, given the difficulty of funding less tangible outcomes. To succeed, OAEBUDT must be clear about what new capabilities it can offer to early adopters, so it can make progress towards gaining the necessary critical mass.

Appendix: Case Study Interviewees

Case Study Interviewees

C&E's case study interviews were held with the participants listed below. Unless otherwise indicated, participants each participated in both pre- and post-integration sessions.

Interviewee Name / Role	Organization
Jayshree Bhakta , Lead QA Engineer Devin O'Hara , Associate Director, Data Engineering	JSTOR
Mirela Roncevic , Head of Content*	Knowledge Unlatched
Tim Lloyd , CEO Michelle Urberg , Client Success**	LibLynx
Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei , Co-Director	punctum books
Peter Potter , VP for Open Access Publishing, Paradigm Francisco de Virgilio , Chief Technology Officer, Ubiquity Rowan Hatherly , DevOps Engineer, Ubiquity**	Ubiquity Press (Paradigm Publishing Services)
Charles Watkinson , Director Pre-integration interviews included members of the Fulcrum Steering Group	Michigan Publishing

*Pre-integration interview only (direct integration not completed by Knowledge Unlatched)

**Post-integration interview only

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